

Protocol for bradykinesia characterization through the relationship between the movement initiation and the termination of the preceding movement

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Abstract— Bradykinesia is one of the motor symptoms of Parkinson's Disease (PD) and it is defined as the slowness in movement. This symptom is also related to two others: akinesia (the difficulty to initiate a movement) and hypokinesia (the decrease in the movement amplitude). One feature of PD is the difficulty to initiate volitional movement. In the literature, it has been raised the question rather this difficulty is due to prejudice at the end of the preceding movement/posture or to the impairment at the beginning of a new movement. Seeking deeper research in the literature about the relationship between the difficulty of initiating volitional movement and the impaired completion of the preceding movement, a literature review has shown a gap in this subject, moreover when it is referred to tasks involving multi-joint movements. Therefore, this work aims to be the starting point to elucidate the mentioned topics, presenting a protocol for the characterization of bradykinesia in subjects with PD through the evaluation of the relationship between the movement initiation and the termination of preceding movement in upper limbs while performing multi-joint tasks. This protocol has been designed based on a literature review and it consists of the following steps: electromyographic acquisition including temporal and inertial variables, description of the tasks involving multi-joint movement to be performed, design for tasks performance, and data analysis. Finally, this experimental protocol will be applied to healthy subjects and patients diagnosed with PD. With the application of this protocol, it is expected to better comprehend the factors behind the difficulty of initiating volitional movements, as well as to identify muscular and kinematic patterns related to bradykinesia. The knowledge of this relationship will support future studies to develop and seek technology/intervention that help people with PD.

Keywords — Protocol, Parkinson's Disease, Bradykinesia, Movement Termination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's Disease is a chronic neurodegenerative disorder of the central nervous system (CNS), specifically of the basal ganglia, and involves the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, causing a decrease in the dopamine level in the striatum and leading to abnormal motor control [1], [2]. Its prevalence is 0.3% of the world population, 1% of people above 60 years old, and 4% of people even older. It is estimated that around 6.3 million people suffer from PD worldwide [3].

The disease is characterized by cardinal motor symptoms, namely: tremor (oscillatory involuntary movements),

bradykinesia (movement's slowness and hesitation), rigidity (increase in muscular tone), and posture instability (loss of balance). Furthermore, the clinical condition may include other motor and non-motor symptoms [4]. It has no cure, however, there are several interventions to alleviate motor symptoms, and they include medication and surgeries [5]. The current clinical standard used for the evaluation of PD symptoms is through scales and questionnaires, in which patterns are obtained based on observation. The most used scale is the *Movement Disorders Society - Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS)* [6].

Bradykinesia is known as the most reliable clinical sign for PD diagnosis [7]. The term bradykinesia is sometimes referred to as a synonym of akinesia or hypokinesia, however, these are distinct terms. Specifically, bradykinesia describes the slowness of a performed movement, whereas akinesia refers to the absence or lack of spontaneous movement or associated movement (for example: freezing or taking longer to initiate movement), and hypokinesia is related to the fact that the amplitude of movement is smaller than desired [8].

One of the PD features is the difficulty to initiate volitional movement (akinesia), as mentioned before [9]. In their study, Warabi *et al.* (2011) questioned whether this difficulty is due to prejudice at the end of the previous movement/posture or to the impairment at the initiation of a new movement. Regarding the latter option, several previous studies have shown how the difficulty hinges on problems in the movement initialization [8], [10], [11].

On the other hand, willing to verify their first hypothesis, Werabi *et al.* (2011) have examined an issue related to eye-hand coordinated movements. They used two types of visually-guided stimuli: one for conditioning and another for testing, using conditions to simulate real-life visual effects (lacuna and superposition tasks). Their results concluded that prolonged manual and ocular latencies in patients with PD, in the superposition task, reflect the difficulty to terminate the preceding movement/posture. The movement initialization had less prejudice than the movement ending [9], [12].

Seeking deeper research in the literature about the relationship between the difficulty of initiating volitional movement and the impaired completion of the preceding movement, it was performed a systematic literature review that has shown a gap in this subject, moreover when it is referred to tasks involving multi-joint movements [13], considering that Werabi *et al.* (2011) have done their work

with single-joint movement. In addition, bradykinesia becomes more prominent in PD while complex (multi-joint) movement is performed [14], [15], [16], reinforcing the importance of investigating this relationship.

Hence, this work aims to be the starting point to elucidate the mentioned topics, presenting a protocol for the characterization of bradykinesia in subjects with PD through the evaluation of the relationship between the initiation and the termination of preceding movement in upper limbs while performing multi-joint tasks.

II. METHODS

The present protocol has been designed based on other studies [9], [17], [18]. Despite the lack of other similar work seeking the same mentioned goal, this protocol was inspired by other experimental protocols and it consists of the following steps: electromyographic acquisition including temporal and inertial variables, description of the tasks involving multi-joint movement to be performed, design for tasks performance, and data analysis. Finally, this experimental protocol will be applied to healthy subjects and patients diagnosed with PD.

III. RESULTS

A. Protocol

• Surface electromyography

In order to have an EMG acquisition with minimum interference and a good electrode fixation, participants' muscle activity recording will be performed following the steps standardized by the SENIAM - *Surface Electromyography for the Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles* [17]. The signal from muscle activity will be captured using a set of EMG sensors - TRIGNO Wireless System (Delsys, USA).

According to the goal of this investigation, activity will be acquired from the upper limb muscles involved in multi-joint tasks (box and block test and nine-hole peg test). Thus, the choice of muscles was based on the proximal and distal muscles recruited during the movement performance, namely: the upper portion of the trapezius muscle, the anterior and posterior portions of the deltoid, pectoralis major, biceps brachii, triceps brachii, extensor carpi radialis brevis, and flexor digitorum superficialis. These are selected muscles because of their main roles in the stabilization and movement of the shoulder and elbow joints. The latter two muscles were chosen because of their functions in wrist positioning and finger movements, as described in the literature [18]. Table 1 lists the corresponding movements for each muscle.

In addition, a Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) superficial electromyograph will be collected from each muscle. Participants will be requested to perform a maximum isometric contraction three times under manual resistance for 10 s, with an interval of 2 min between trials to avoid fatigue [18]. A dynamometer will be used to acquire the MVC signal for the flexor digitorum superficialis. The arithmetical average from the three trials, expressed in microvolts, will be calculated and used as reference for 100% of electromyographic muscular activity. The MVC will be useful for normalizing EMG data [19].

TABLE I. SELECTED MUSCLES AND CORRESPONDING MOVEMENTS.

Muscle	Movement
Trapezius (upper fibers)	Scapular adduction, elevation, and upward rotation.
Deltoid (anterior fibers)	Shoulder flexion, medial rotation, and abduction.
Deltoid (posterior fibers)	Shoulder extension, lateral rotation, and abduction.
Pectoralis Major	Shoulder adduction and medial rotation.
Biceps Brachii	Elbow flexion and forearm supination.
Triceps Brachii	Elbow extension.
Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis	Wrist extension.
Flexor Digitorum Superficialis	Flexion of the proximal interphalangeal joints.

• Inertial Sensors

The acquisition of the subjects' temporal and inertial variables (displacement, acceleration, and speed) while performing the tasks will be performed using the same sensors used for electromyography because they are also equipped with a gyroscope, magnetometer, and accelerometer.

• Description of tasks

After placing the sensors on the participants, tasks will begin to be performed: a box and block test for obtaining information from gross multi-joint movements, and a nine-hole peg test for information from fine muscular activity in complex movements. Participants will be seated in a height-adjustable chair with no armrest and will be instructed to seat resting their feet on the floor and hips and knees flexed at 90° [20]. Before a trial begins, participants will be required to place both arms on the table and maintain this position until they have the maximum relaxation level, which will be visually tracked by EMG signal recording. At that moment, the task will be prompted to start using a sound command.

- Box and block test

Participants must transfer the 2.5 cm wooden cubes from one side of the box to the other as quickly as possible using only their dominant hand (Fig. 1A). They will hear two beeps; the first indicates that they can begin transferring the blocks, and the second indicates that they must stop transferring and rest their hand on the table while awaiting the next start signal. To prevent the participant from learning the timing of the signal and anticipating the movement, there will be a total of five stops, and the duration of time during which the individual performs the task or rests will vary between 30 s and 1 min. If the block is in the air at the moment of the stop signal, the subject must place it on the side of the nearest box and then place their hand on the table.

- Nine-Hole Peg Test

In this task, the research participants will have to put thin 7 mm pegs in each hole of the pegboard (Fig. 1B) as quickly as possible and then removed. They will follow the same protocol for performing the box and block task, repeating the process of placing and removing the pins until the five stops are completed.

Fig 1 – A) Box and block test. B) Nine-hole peg test.

- Design for task performance

Figure 2 illustrates the entire data collection process, which will be concluded after five stops for each task. Subjects will be presented with both sound commands and, as mentioned before, the duration time in which the individual performs the task or rest will be random from 30 s to 1 min, so that the participant does not learn the moment of the signal and anticipates the movement.

- Data analysis

The generated electromyography data will be recorded using EMGWorks software. Then, these data will be transferred to R programming language software and will be windowed, filtered, and processed to extract and analyze the features of the signal, seeking to characterize bradykinesia by evaluating the initialization and termination of the previous movement. The data from the inertial sensors will also be processed using R programming language software. For statistical analysis, a correlation will be made between the signal at the beginning of the movement (X in Fig. 2) and the signal at the end of the previous movement (Y in Fig. 2). For intragroup and intergroup comparisons, a normality test will be carried out initially, and depending on the behavior of the

sample, parametric (normal sample) and non-parametric (non-normal sample) statistical tests will be performed with a significance level of 5%.

B. Protocol Application

The study protocol will be applied to 60 individuals. The number of participants was defined based on similar works in the literature [9] [12]. These 60 subjects will be divided into two distinct groups: a test group composed of 30 subjects diagnosed with PD and a control group composed of 30 healthy subjects that will be matched with the test group by age. For patients with PD, the protocol will be applied in two stages: in the OFF state, that is, without medication for a period of 12 hours, and in the ON state, with the use of medication.

The execution of the study will comply with the rules of the National Health Council through Resolution No. 466/2012, which establishes guidelines and regulatory standards for research involving human beings. The beginning of the protocol will only take place after approval by the Ethics Committee in Research with Human Beings, completion and signing of the Free and Informed Consent Term, and signing of the authorization term for the use of videos and secondary data.

- Control group

Thirty healthy volunteers will be included in this study group. The inclusion criteria will be as follows: age paired with the individual in the test group (between 18 and 80 years), no disease related to motor disorder, and no sequelae from a previous upper limb musculoskeletal injury. The exclusion criterion will be the lack of understanding of the instructions provided in the protocol.

- Test group

In this group, 30 patients diagnosed with PD will be recruited. The inclusion criteria will be as follows: diagnosis of PD, bradykinesia, age between 18 and 80 years, and no sequelae from a previous upper limb musculoskeletal injury. Participants who did not understand the instructions provided in the protocol will be excluded.

IV. DISCUSSION

The elaboration of this protocol was based on an in-depth study of the literature for elaboration of each step according to the objective to be investigated, that is, to characterize bradykinesia in individuals with PD by evaluating the relationship between the initiation and termination of preceding movement in the upper limbs during multi-joint tasks.

Fig 2 - Outline of execution for each task. S1 = sound stimulus to start movement. S2 = sound stimulus to stop movement and rest.

The execution of the electromyographic evaluation must be preceded by standardization, where the muscles that will be evaluated, the equipment used, the preparation for the collection, positioning of the electrodes, posture of the individuals and the activities that will be carried out must be pre-established [21]. Precise definition of the muscles and procedures for normalization of the electromyographic signal are very important [22]. Therefore, the development and use of a protocol is important so that the recording of electromyographic activity faithfully represents the electrical signal of the muscles that will be studied.

The first step, before starting the assessment, is to define the muscles or muscle groups to be analyzed. These must be selected according to the purpose of the study and movements that will be performed [21]. Based on the multi-joint movements of the upper limbs, the muscles were selected according to their main roles in the stabilization and movement of the shoulder and elbow joints as well as their functions in wrist and finger movements [20], [23-25].

The box and block test consists of repeatedly moving 2.5 cm wooden cubes from one box to another when placed side by side [26]. The nine-hole peg test measures hand dexterity by placing 7 mm diameter wooden pegs on a pegboard as quickly as possible [27]. The selection of tests was based on the type of motor task required for the final work objective, which results in multi-joint upper-limb movements considered complex, which also requires manual dexterity [28-29].

The sound stimulus was selected considering the need to perform the motor tasks so that the participants would have freedom of movement, unlike a visual stimulus, and it would not interfere with the final objective with the application of the protocol. The stimulus referred to as "S1" (beginning) - a high-pitched sound (target: 2000 Hz and 80 dB) or the stimulus "S2" - a low-frequency sound (default: 1000 Hz and 80 dB) - will be presented [30].

V. CONCLUSION

With the elaboration and application of this protocol, it will be possible to characterize bradykinesia by evaluating this relationship; thus, it will be possible to elucidate the factors responsible for the difficulty in initiating volitional movements as well as identify muscular and kinematic patterns related to bradykinesia. Knowledge of this relationship will serve as a basis for future studies to develop and seek technologies/interventions to help people with PD.

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